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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Trainings	1
2.1 Science to Business Camp	1
2.1.1 Objectives	2
2.1.2 Venues	2
2.1.3 Materials	2
2.2 Open Science Communication 2022	2
2.2.1 Objectives	3
2.2.2 Venues	3
2.2.3 Materials	3
2.3 Patent protection	4
2.3.1 Objectives	4
2.3.2 Venues	5
2.3.3 Materials	5
2.4 Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission	6
Full title of the training: Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission	6
2.4.1 Objectives	6
2.4.2 Venues	6
2.4.3 Materials	6
2.5 Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe	7
2.5.1 Objectives	7
2.5.2 Venues	8
2.5.3 Materials	8
2.6 Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia	9
2.6.1 Objectives	9
2.6.2 Venues	9
2.6.3 Materials	9
2.7 Manage all your projects efficiently	10
2.7.1 Objectives	11
2.7.2 Venues	11
2.7.3 Materials	11
2.8 Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe Projects	11
2.8.1 Objectives	12
2.8.2 Venues	12
2.8.3 Materials	12
2.9 Grant Management in Horizon Europe	13

2.9.1	Objectives	13
2.9.2	Venues	14
2.9.3	Materials	14
2.10	Basics of budget in Horizon Europe	14
2.10.1	Objectives	15
2.10.2	Venues	15
2.10.3	Materials	15
2.11	Procurement Open Forum and Q&A	16
2.11.1	Objectives	16
2.11.2	Venues	17
2.11.3	Materials	17
2.12	How to apply to Horizon Europe	18
2.12.1	Objectives	19
2.12.2	Venues	19
2.12.3	Materials	19
2.13	Researcher Management and Leadership Training	20
2.13.1	Objectives	20
2.13.2	Venues	20
2.13.3	Materials	20
3.	Conclusion	21

List of Figures

Figure 1 Photo of BIOS researcher at the Science to Business Camp	2
Figure 2 Photos of BIOS researchers at the Open Science Communication Conference	4
Figure 3 Screenshots from “Patent protection of innovative technical solutions” training	5
Figure 4 Screenshots from “How to decide” session during “Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission” training	6
Figure 5 Screenshots from “How to avoid” session during “Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission” training	7
Figure 7 Screenshots from “Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe - how does it work?” training	8
Figure 8 Screenshots from “Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia” training	10
Figure 9 Screenshots from “EMDESK – Manage all your projects efficiently – in one place” training	11
Figure 10 Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe training agenda	12
Figure 11 Screenshots from “Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe” training	13
Figure 12 Screenshots from “Horizon Implementation Day: Grant Management in Horizon Europe” training	14
Figure 13 Screenshots “Enspire Science - Basics of budget in Horizon Europe” training	16
Figure 14 Photo of BIOS researchers at Procurement Open Forum and Q&A	17
Figure 15 Photo of BIOS project manager delivering a presentation	18
Figure 16 Screenshots from “How to apply to Horizon Europe” training	19
Figure 17 Obtained certificates from “Researcher Management and Leadership Training” course	21

1. Introduction

The primary objective of the NANOFACTS project is to enhance research excellence at the BioSense Institute, specifically focusing on the development of nanomaterials for applications in cancer therapy, imaging, and diagnosis. Additionally, the project aims to strengthen biosensor technology capacities by advancing research in biosensors for cancer detection. Elevating overall research excellence involves reinforcing research management and administration (RMA) skills, starting with refining project writing skills in the initial stages, extending to networking and collaboration for consortium formation, and continuing through the implementation phase. This phase encompasses activities such as public procurement, which may pose challenges for young researchers without prior experience.

NANOFACTS addresses this need by providing comprehensive training across all stages of research project preparation and implementation, including potential technology transfer. These training sessions aim to equip BioSense researchers with practical experience in RMA activities. This deliverable summarizes the trainings conducted in the third year of the project. These trainings covered various aspects, addressing general challenges in project proposal writing, management, implementation, and dissemination. Their design ensures their relevance and value for researchers at the BioSense Institute.

2. Trainings

One of the main objectives of NANOFACTS's activities within Work Package 5 is to organize specific trainings for all BioSense (BIOS) researchers.

The focus of the third year of the NANOFACTS project was on various training events, providing BIOS researchers with opportunities to learn about project proposal writing, project management, implementation, dissemination, procurement open forum, and intellectual property (IP).

2.1 Science to Business Camp

Full title of the event: “Science to Business Camp”

From the 17th to 20th of August 2022, Mirjana Mundžić, a member of the NANOFACTS TEAM from BioSense Institute participated in the “Science to Business Camp” in Smolenice Castle, Slovakia, organized by @inovato.sk Cluster.

The Camp aimed to bridge the gap between Science and Business by inviting researchers (students and postgraduates) and business professionals to discuss and define strategies for commercializing their research, making it accessible to the public, and generating revenue.

During the camp, Mirjana actively engaged in over 15 lectures and workshops conducted by 10 speakers. These sessions covered a wide range of topics, including the commercialization of scientific research, preparing of idea presentations and financial planning, protecting intellectual property rights, selecting funding sources, and more. Particularly valuable were the success stories shared by Stephen Russo, the author of the book 'Commercialization of Science,' and Pavol Cekan,

the director of MultiplexDX, an innovative biotechnology company specializing in molecular biology, biochemistry, and oncology.

2.1.1 Objectives

- Understand the process of bridging science with business.
- Acquire knowledge on commercializing research for public use and profitability.
- Enable direct interaction between participants and experienced presenters.
- Conduct Q&A sessions for further clarification and engagement.

2.1.2 Venues

The event took place in person from the 17th to 20th of August 2022 at the Congress Centre of SAS Smolenice, Slovakia.

Link: <https://inova.to/en/event/science-to-business-camp/>

2.1.3 Materials

Information about this event was discovered online, providing details on its schedule, participants, and key activities. Mirjana actively engaged in over 15 lectures and workshops conducted by 10 distinct speakers during the Camp (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Photo of BIOS researcher at the Science to Business Camp

2.2 Open Science Communication 2022

Full title of the webinar: Open Science Communication Conference – OpenSciComm 2022

Open science communication is vital for fostering transparency, collaboration, and innovation in scientific projects. It ensures that research methods and findings are accessible, promoting reproducibility and trust within the scientific community. Additionally, open communication enhances public engagement, making scientific advancements more understandable and impactful for a broader audience.

In line with these the compelling reasons, NANOFACTS young researchers actively engaged in the Open Science Communication Conference hosted by the Serbian Center for the Promotion of Science on November 24-25, 2022. This strategic participation aligns with our project's commitment to transparency, collaboration, and innovative scientific communication methodologies.

2.2.1 Objectives

- Gain insights from Open Science Communication keynotes.
- Explore “Open Science in the open world”.
- Engage with the lecture titled “In Science We Trust”.
- Delve into the Secret of Masonic communication and more.
- Participate in the lecture: “Open Science: Unlock your Research for multilayered audiences and resources”.
- Conduct Q&A sessions for further clarification and engagement.

2.2.2 Venues

The Open Science Communication Conference – OpenSciComm 2022, organized by the Serbian Center for the Promotion of Science took place from November 24th to 25th, 2022, at the Yugoslav Film Archive CPN Scientific Club, Belgrade, Serbia.

Link: <https://int.cpn.edu.rs/en/open-science-communication-2022/#konf>

2.2.3 Materials

The Serbian Center for the Promotion of Science extended invitations for conference participation via email.

The conference was attended by two (2) NANOFACTS’s researchers, Aleksandra Pavlović and Stefan Jarić (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Photos of BIOS researchers at the Open Science Communication Conference

2.3 Patent protection

Full title of the training: Patent protection of innovative technical solutions

On March 17, 2023, Dr Slavica Savić attended a lecture titled “Patent protection of innovative technical solutions” delivered by Natasa Milovanović from the Institute for Intellectual Property of Republic of Serbia. During the session, Mrs Milovanović presented numerous examples illustrating how to recognize true technical solutions that are eligible for patent protection.

2.3.1 Objectives

- Understand the concept of patent protection.
- Familiarize oneself with the fundamental principles of the patent system.
- Gain insight into crucial aspects of the patent protection procedure.

2.3.2 Venues

The training was held online on March 17, 2023, through Zoom online platform.

The used link:

<https://us02web.zoom.us/j/81960785411?pwd=bXpocTAOVTRCclFIK1JXVDVMZVVuQT09#success>

2.3.3 Materials

The presentation for the training (refer to Figure 3) was conducted by Nataša Milovanović, from the Institute for Intellectual Property of Republic of Serbia. She also works as a head of international cooperation at the State Intellectual Property Office of the Republic of Serbia.

The training was attended by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from BioSense, Dr. Slavica Savić.

Figure 3 Screenshots from “Patent protection of innovative technical solutions” training

2.4 Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission

Full title of the training: Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission

On April 25, 2023, a NANOFACTS team member, Dr Slavica Savić participated in the training organized by Europa Media (Figures 4 and 5).

The session primarily explored the feasibility of altering the entire project concept a month before submission or modifying the structure of the work plan two weeks before the deadline. Practical tips and strategies for navigating such challenging scenarios were provided during the session.

2.4.1 Objectives

- Explore the feasibility of altering the entire project concept shortly before submission.
- Investigate the possibility of changing the work plan structure two weeks before the submission deadline.
- Acquire practical tips and strategies for addressing such challenging situations.
- Facilitate direct interaction between participants and the speaker.
- Conduct a Q&A session for further clarification and engagement.

2.4.2 Venues

The training about Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission was organized online on April 25, 2023, through Zoom online platform.

The used link: <https://us02web.zoom.us/j/82046701846>

2.4.3 Materials

The invitation for the training was sent by NANOFACTS's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, to the BioSense project team via email. The training was attended by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from BioSense, Dr. Slavica Savić.

Figure 4 Screenshots from “How to decide” session during “Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission” training

Figure 5 Screenshots from “How to avoid” session during “Last-Minute Changes Before Horizon Europe Proposal Submission” training

2.5 Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe

Full title of the training: Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe - how does it work?

Horizon Europe has extended the implementation of the Lump Sum budget model as part of its efforts to streamline program complexities. Anticipated to see further growth in the future, it becomes imperative to acquaint oneself with this funding model. The present course has been tailored for participants already well-versed in the Horizon Europe Actual Cost model, aiming to impart knowledge about the Lump Sum model.

Throughout the course organized by Enspire Science on September 27, 2023, participants had the opportunity to delve deeper into the fundamental budgetary aspects of the Lump Sum model. The course also included the provision of practical recommendations and tips to assist researchers in the process of formulating their own Lump Sum proposals, as illustrated in Figure 6.

2.5.1 Objectives

- Stay informed about Horizon Europe's budget models.
- Educate participants about the specifics of the Lump Sum model.
- Explore the fundamental budgetary aspects underlying the Lump Sum model.
- Provide practical recommendations and tips to support researchers in crafting their own Lump Sum proposals.
- Conduct a Q&A session for further clarification and engagement.

2.5.2 Venues

The training “Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe - how does it work?” was organized by Enspire Science, and it was held online 2023 through Zoom online platform.

The used link:

https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85884020807?tk=AozzwqizYgGvNNcpYThbkiOKm7EDYK7RMxZlocUAc6M.DQQAAAAT_xYoRxZlc2VydTIPYIJGaVFVQnRRZXkZGhBAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA&uuid=WN_oAuXvkPTTo2agtTYCj7eg

2.5.3 Materials

Information about the training was disseminated by NANOFACT's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, who extended an invitation for the training to the BioSense project team via email.

The training was attended by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from BioSense, Dr. Slavica Savić.

Figure 6 Screenshots from “Lump sum funding in Horizon Europe - how does it work?” training

2.6 Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia

Full title of the training: Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia

On October 10, 2023, Dr. Slavica Savić participated in an online training course titled "Research Assessment and Open Science Practices in Serbia." The event was hosted virtually by the University of Belgrade, the University of Novi Sad, and the Open Science Community in Serbia.

The event revolved around a comprehensive discussion regarding the status of Open Science (OS) practices in the country. It commenced with an overview of the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) policy regulations in Serbia, leveraging current initiatives and assessing challenges that the Serbian research community still needs to address, notably focusing on platforms like the eNauka portal. The debate was stimulated by presentations on the GraspOS and OPUS projects, as well as by FAIR-IMPACT partners who provided insights into the FAIR-IMPACT contribution to FAIR assessment practices.

The training was conducted by Natalia Galica (National Science Center, Poland), Ingrid Dillo (Deputy Director at Data Archiving and Networked Services, Netherlands), and Biljana Kosanovic (University of Belgrade, Serbia).

2.6.1 Objectives

- To provide an overview of FAIR policy regulations in Serbia
- Leverage current initiatives in Open Science practices
- To assess challenges within the Serbian research community, particularly focusing on platforms like the eNauka portal
- To stimulate debate through presentations on GraspOS and OPUS projects, along with insights from FAIR-IMPACT partners on contributions to FAIR assessment practices

2.6.2 Venues

The training about Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia was organized by University of Belgrade, the University of Novi Sad, and the Open Science Community in Serbia.

It was held online through the following link:

<https://fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows/open-science-and-research-data-management-policies-serbia>

2.6.3 Materials

Information about the training was available on the FAIR-IMPACT website: <https://fair-impact.eu/>.

The training was followed by one (1) NANOFACTS researcher from the BioSense, Dr Slavica Savić (Figure 7).

Figure 7 Screenshots from “Research Assessment and Open Science practices in Serbia” training

2.7 Manage all your projects efficiently

Full title of the training: EMDESK – Manage all your projects efficiently – in one place.

On October 17, 2023, researchers from NANOFACT attended a webinar on the efficient management of projects organized by EMDESK. The webinar aimed to introduce a comprehensive solution addressing the challenges of project and financial management through developed software. This software serves as a single, flexible platform empowering project team to collaborate effectively while maintaining control and transparency throughout the project lifecycle.

The software offers tools for designing and budgeting projects of any scale, ensuring that project teams can create and manage project plans efficiently. Its collaborative features enhance productivity by facilitating real-time communication, file sharing, and task assignment, all within the platform. The webinar highlighted the software's capacity to streamline document creation and collaboration. Attendees observed how teams could collaborate on documents in real time, improving version control and reducing inefficiencies.

Furthermore, the webinar demonstrated the software's powerful analytics tools, showcasing its ability to provide project managers with essential data and insights for making informed decisions.

This webinar proved valuable for NANOFACT's young researchers, offering them insights into efficient project management and organization, thereby preparing them for future project leadership.

2.7.1 Objectives

- To introduce a comprehensive software solution for efficient project and financial management.
- Highlight the collaborative tools within the platform to enhance real-time communication, file sharing, and task assignment.
- Emphasize the software's ability to streamline document creation and collaboration, improving version control and reducing inefficiencies.
- Pool about biggest challenges in project management
- Prepare NANOFACT's young researchers for future project leadership by imparting knowledge on efficient project management and organization.

2.7.2 Venues

The webinar on efficient management organized by EMDESK was held online on October 17, 2023, using the Zoom platform.

The used link:

https://eu01web.zoom.us/j/87496873520?tk=bV5BQPbcci9PlsaDUV40T82lcrOorws7TnUMK5nggYs.DQQAAAAUXzhWMBZVMER3WmJDYVMxU0tnbVFZbTJQUUnN3AAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA&uuid=WN_owgHJyh8S0efxA0emxGKYg

2.7.3 Materials

The information about the webinar on the efficient management of projects was shared by Mila Djisalov, NANOFACT's WP5 leader, who extended an invitation for the training to the BioSense project team via email.

The webinar was followed by three (3) NANOFACTS's researchers from the BioSense, Mila Djisalov, Ivana Kundačina and Teodora Knežić.

Figure 8 Screenshots from “EMDESK – Manage all your projects efficiently – in one place” training

2.8 Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe Projects

Full title of the training: Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe: How does it work? How to write a lump sum proposal?

As previously highlighted, Horizon Europe has expanded the implementation of the Lump Sum budget model to simplify program complexities. On October 19, 2023, the European Commission organized a training session to provide practical guidance on writing lump sum proposal.

The first part of the training encompassed a fundamental introduction to Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe, elucidating its mechanisms and insights into crafting proposals. The subsequent part involved sharing practical experiences with lump sum grants. Finally, a Q&A session allowed participants to directly pose questions to European Commission members regarding their most significant challenges in project preparation.

2.8.1 Objectives

- Expand the utilization of the Lump Sum budget model in Horizon Europe to simplify program procedures.
- Provide practical guidance on writing lump sum proposals through a Commission-led training.
- Deliver a fundamental introduction to Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe
- Share real-life experiences with lump sum grants and facilitate a Q&A session to address project challenges.

2.8.2 Venues

The training entitled “Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe: How does it work? How to write a lump sum proposal?” was organized by European Commission on October 19, 2023, and it was held online by using YouTube live streaming.

The link for YouTube video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zKC1CRax8co&t=1s>

2.8.3 Materials

Paula Valente Correia, Research Program Manager from the European Commission, communicated training details to NANOFACT's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, who subsequently forwarded the information via email.

The training was followed by two (2) NANOFACTS's researchers from the BioSense, Maša Mimica and Dr Nikola Knežević (Figure 9 and 10).

Figure 9 Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe training agenda

Figure 10 Screenshots from “Lump Sum Funding in Horizon Europe” training

2.9 Grant Management in Horizon Europe

Full title of the training: Horizon Implementation Day: Grant Management in Horizon Europe

On October 24, 2023, the European Commission organized a training session about Grant Management in Horizon Europe. The training provided comprehensive insights into Grant Management in Horizon Europe, covering all important aspects needed for successful project implementation. Topics covered include amendments, project lifetime and reporting, payments, project results, etc. This training holds significant importance for researchers as it equips them with the necessary knowledge and skills to effectively navigate and manage their projects within Horizon Europe.

2.9.1 Objectives

- Provide in-depth insights into Grant Management in Horizon Europe.
- Cover key parameters for successful project implementation.
- Equip researchers with vital skills for effective project management under Horizon Europe

2.9.2 Venues

The training about Grant Management in Horizon Europe was organized by European Commission on October 24, 2023, and it was held online by using YouTube live streaming.

The link for YouTube video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BWljLBZnrDI>

2.9.3 Materials

Paula Valente Correia, Research Program Manager from the European Commission, communicated training details to NANOFACT's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, who subsequently forwarded the information via email.

The training was followed by NANOFACTS's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević and Dr. Slavica Savić (Figure 11).

Figure 11 Screenshots from “Horizon Implementation Day: Grant Management in Horizon Europe” training

2.10 Basics of budget in Horizon Europe

Full title of the training: Enspire Science - Basics of budget in Horizon Europe

On October 26, 2023, Enspire Science organized an online event titled "Basics of Budget in Horizon Europe." The event focused on Lump Sum grants and actual cost models, highlighting their distinctive approach to funding compared to reimbursement-based or performance-based models. These grants, commonly awarded to companies and institutes, provide a predetermined sum of money upfront, enabling recipients to plan their expenditures with increased flexibility.

The training covered the principles behind lump sum grants, underscoring the significance of simplifying financial processes and encouraging efficient resource allocation. Implementation of this funding model necessitates ensuring fair and goal-aligned funding rates for companies and institutes. In the context of budget preparation, close collaboration with financial and accounting departments is essential to accurately assess funding requirements, allocate resources, and monitor financial performance. Emphasizing a collaborative approach, it was noted that this strategy optimizes the utilization of lump sum grants, fostering financial stability and facilitating strategic growth.

2.10.1 Objectives

- To Outline Lump Sum grants and actual cost models in Horizon Europe
- To highlight their distinctive funding approach compared to other models
- Showcase increased flexibility in planning expenditures with Lump Sum grants
- To emphasize principles for simplifying financial processes
- To stress out the importance of fair and goal-aligned funding rates through collaborative budget preparation
- Q&A session

2.10.2 Venues

The training entitled "Enspire Science - Basics of budget in Horizon Europe" was organized by Enspire Science on October 26, 2023, and it was held online by using Zoom platform.

The used link:

https://us02web.zoom.us/j/85160055523?tk=MyLOQskLUXJSwA4Sd30ooS0N7_RdRYqTx6jREz3bTZI.DQUAAAAT0-9S4xZmSmRyQzhaS1NBZXJUbVZ6UUZUcDhRAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA&uuid=WN_Y99_xrxMRAaGpzqV-Mz_fw

2.10.3 Materials

The information about the training was shared by Mila Djisalov, NANOFACT's WP5 leader, who extended an invitation for the training to the BioSense project team via email. The training was followed by seven (7) NANOFACTS's researchers from the BioSense, Mirjana Mundžić, Dr Slavica Savić, Dr Ivana Gadjanski, Mila Djisalov, Teodora Knežić, Aleksandra Pavlović and Nejra Omerović. At Figure 12 the screenshots from the training are provided.

Figure 12 Screenshots “Enspire Science - Basics of budget in Horizon Europe” training

2.11 Procurement Open Forum and Q&A

Full title of the training: Procurement Open Forum and Q&A

On November 3, 2023, the BioSense Institute organized the Procurement Open Forum and Q&A. This event, coordinated by BioSense’s Center for Innovation and Business Development and led by presenter Bojan Gavrilović, aimed to acquaint BioSense researchers with key challenges associated with procurement planning processes. The forum covered topics such as Dynamic Purchasing Systems, Framework Agreements, and project budget planning.

2.11.1 Objectives

- Familiarize BioSense's researchers with challenges in procurement planning processes
- Provide insights into Dynamic Purchasing Systems and Framework Agreements
- Enhance understanding of project budget planning through the Procurement Open Forum and Q&A

2.11.2 Venues

The Procurement Open Forum and Q&A event was organized in person on November 3, 2023, in the amphitheatre of BioSense's new building in Novi Sad, Serbia.

2.11.3 Materials

The information about the event was provided by Bojan Gavrilović, Senior Expert Associate in the field of public procurement, from the Center for Innovation and Business Development, through an email. The training was followed by seven (7) NANOFACTS's researchers, and 42 BioSense's researchers in total (Figures 13 and 14).

Figure 13 Photo of BIOS researchers at Procurement Open Forum and Q&A

Figure 14 Photo of BIOS project manager delivering a presentation

2.12 How to apply to Horizon Europe

Full title of the training: How to apply to Horizon Europe

On November 14, 2023, a training session on 'How to Apply to Horizon Europe' was conducted as part of the Support Programme for the Development of Digital Innovation Hubs in the Western Balkans, led by the Regional Cooperation Council Secretariat (RCC) in collaboration with Econet (FundingBox Group). This well-structured session aimed to comprehensively guide participants through the Horizon Europe application process. Beginning with an overview of Horizon Europe and initial proposal requirements, the training delved into the components of a Horizon Europe proposal, offering focused guidance on Excellence, Impact, and Implementation in different segments. The intelligently divided webinar dedicated specific time to unravel the complexities of constructing a Horizon Europe budget. This strategic approach facilitated effective absorption of information, allowing participants to progress from foundational understanding to the nuanced skills required for crafting a successful project proposal.

2.12.1 Objectives

- Provide comprehensive guidance through the Horizon Europe application process
- Deliver focused insights into the components of a Horizon Europe proposal, emphasizing Excellence, Impact, and Implementation
- Facilitate effective absorption of information by intelligently dividing the webinar to address the complexities of constructing a Horizon Europe budget, enabling participants to develop nuanced skills for crafting successful project proposals

2.12.2 Venues

The training was organized by Regional Cooperation Council Secretariat (RCC) in collaboration with Econet (FundingBox Group), and it was held online on November 14th by using Zoom platform.

The used link:

https://us06web.zoom.us/j/83903047483?tk=6tIabvIPYBktKS7xWOkNoTq65C9X5uR2vVeFLpbuxU.DQUAAAATiQLnOxZWzi1uZIJCVFetcWthNEp6V1RNM09BAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAAA&uuiid=WN_QBf62MTRQC8xzmWp9dsA

2.12.3 Materials

Information about the training was provided by was shared by Milica Trajković, who extended an invitation for the training to the BioSense project team via email.

The training was followed by one (1) NANOFACTS researchers from the BioSense, Minja Mladenović (Figure 15).

Figure 15 Screenshots from “How to apply to Horizon Europe” training

2.13 Researcher Management and Leadership Training

Full title of the training: Researcher Management and Leadership Training

During the period of October to November 2023, four researchers from NANOFACTS successfully completed the Researcher Management and Leadership Training course offered by the University of Colorado, accessible on the global online learning platform, Coursera.

The course provides insights into the importance of management and leadership skills for building a successful research career, emphasizing resource optimization. It covers effective management of research groups, including hiring, team engagement, and fostering a positive culture. Participants gain an understanding of financial and administrative responsibilities, such as regulatory compliance, financial reporting, and budgeting, essential for researchers. Additionally, the course explores the roles of mentors and mentees, guiding participants in strategically building mentorship teams and enhancing mentorship through coaching and sponsorship.

2.13.1 Objectives

- Assess the significance of management and leadership skills for building successful research career
- Gain insights into effective research group management, including hiring and team engagement
- Understand key financial and administrative responsibilities for researchers, covering compliance, reporting, and budgeting
- Learn strategic approaches to mentorship, including building mentorship teams and enhancing mentorship through coaching and sponsorship

2.13.2 Venues

The course is available online at the official Coursera website:

https://www.coursera.org/learn/researcher-management-leadership-training?utm_medium=sem&utm_source=gg&utm_campaign=B2C_EMEA_coursera_FTcoF_career-academy_pmax-nonNRL-within-14d-country-FR&campaignid=20424141964&adgroupid=&device=c&keyword=&matchtype=&network=x&device_model=&adposition=&creativeid=&hide_mobile_promo&gclid=Cj0KCQiAmNegBhD4ARIsADsYfTd5CFPbfcDcXeneTL5uRyz2yggQA_SleoVVfNkgUBTjPwULRSxQRikaApzREALw_wcB

2.13.3 Materials

NANOFACTS's coordinator, Dr. Nikola Knežević, provided information via email about available courses that can be of great importance for project implementation and the development of research management and administration (RMA) skills for participating researchers. The course was attended by four (4) researchers from NANOFACTS at BioSense: Dr Nikola Knežević, Dr Slavica Savić, Minja Mladenović and Mirjana Mundžić who were subsequently awarded certificates (Figure 16).

Figure 16 Obtained certificates from “Researcher Management and Leadership Training” course

3. Conclusion

One of the objectives of the NANOFACTS project is to enhance the research management and administration (RMA) skills of participating researchers. This goal aims at empowering them to actively engage in ongoing and emerging research activities, secure additional funding, generate high-quality outcomes and publish them in influential peer-reviewed journals. Consequently, this deliverable has been compiled to provide a summary of all the conducted training sessions and presentations focused on enhancing RMA skills throughout the project's third year of implementation. The training sessions outlined herein have proven invaluable for NANOFACTS team members and researchers at the BioSense Institute.